

Teaching Digital Service Skills and Innovative Behaviour to Fresh Graduates: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract: This study explores the influence of teaching methods of service digitalization and innovative work behaviour models on fresh graduates. In the digital transformation era, the application of information technology is becoming increasingly important to improve work efficiency and effectiveness. This study aims to analyze the extent to which digitalization can encourage innovative work behaviour models and how combining the two can improve the performance of fresh graduate employees. Following a quantitative approach, data was collected through a survey of 300 fresh graduates employed as employees in various government agencies in Indonesia. Data analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression techniques to identify the relationship between the variables studied. The results showed that service digitalization significantly positively impacts employees' innovative work behaviour. In addition, innovative work behaviour was also shown to contribute considerably to improving employee performance. These findings indicate that integrating technology into daily work can encourage innovation and productivity in fresh graduates. This research suggests that government agencies need to continue to encourage the implementation of the teaching method of digital technology and create a work culture that supports innovation. Thus, the performance of fresh graduates as employees can be improved, improving the overall quality.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dijitalleştirme
Yenilikçi çalışma
Yeni mezun
Gençler

Yeni Mezunlara Dijital Hizmet Becerileri ve Yenilikçi Davranışlar Öğretmek: Ampirik Bir Analiz
Özet: Bu araştırma, hizmet dijitalleştirme ve yenilikçi çalışma davranışları modellerinin öğretim yöntemlerinin yeni mezunlar üzerindeki etkisini incelemektedir. Dijital dönüşüm çağında, bilgi teknolojisinin uygulanması iş verimliliğini ve etkinliğini artırmak için giderek daha da önemli hale geldiğinden bu çalışma, dijitalleştirme yenilikçi çalışma davranışları modellerini ne ölçüde teşvik edebileceğini ve ikisinin birleştirilmesinin yeni mezun çalışanların performansını nasıl iyileştirebileceğini analiz etmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Nicel bir yaklaşım izlenerek, Endonezya'daki çeşitli devlet kurumlarında çalışan 300 yeni mezundan anket yoluyla veri toplanmıştır. İncelenen değişkenler arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek için çoklu doğrusal regresyon teknikleri kullanılarak veri analizi yapılmıştır. Sonuçlar, hizmet dijitalleştirilmesinin çalışanların yenilikçi çalışma davranışlarını önemli ölçüde olumlu etkilediğini göstermiştir. Ayrıca, yenilikçi çalışma davranışının çalışan performansını iyileştirmeye önemli ölçüde katkıda bulunduğu da ortaya koymuştur. Ek olarak bulgular, teknolojinin günlük işe entegre edilmesinin yeni mezunlarda yenilikçiliği ve üretkenliği teşvik edebileceğini göstermektedir. Bu araştırma, devlet kurumlarının dijital teknolojinin öğretim yönteminin uygulanmasını teşvik etmeye ve yenilikçiliği destekleyen bir çalışma kültürü yaratmaya devam etmeleri gerektiğini göstermektedir. Böylece, yeni mezunların çalışan olarak performansı iyileştirilebilir ve genel kalite artırılabilir.

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1. Introduction

Digitalization is the most apparent phenomenon that characterizes today's world, where fast and easy dissemination of information is highly valued. Information and communication technologies have been increasingly developing in the last two decades and thus profoundly revolutionizing various sectors. All these have been reshaping our world to lead people to have "access to knowledge and information through multiple and varied media and sources" (Porto, 2010, p. 45). In this sense, digitalizing teaching methods has become a critical strategy many governments adopt to improve efficiency, transparency and accountability (Mustapa *et al.*, 2022). This digital transformation has reshaped governments' interaction with the public along with how freshly graduated young employees perform their duties (Kettl, 2002; Light, 2001). In this context, it becomes essential to understand the way digitization of services can improve the performance of such young employees. Digitalization of teaching methods refers to using various digital technologies or tools to increase the efficiency of any given education system (formal or informal) or program (Olsson, 2019). This method has also improved in-service teaching programs for professional and vocational development in public service sectors (Hofmeister & Pilz, 2020). Therefore, the scope of the digitalization of teaching also incorporates easing public access to teaching methods, reducing bureaucracy, and increasing government responsiveness to the needs of the people (Milakovich, 2011, 2021).

Digitalization of education and teaching offers various benefits, such as increasing operational efficiency and transparency. However, it may also pose some challenges, such as reluctance to change. Fresh graduate employees come into play at this point as they adjust fast to such digital changes. Yet, traditionally practised works or tasks in conventional organizations may make them hesitant to transition to technology-based systems. As a result, developing a work culture that encourages creativity, technology adoption, and creative workplace behaviour is essential. Innovative employees tend to be more flexible to change and successful at using technology to boost performance. Innovative work behaviour depends on individual abilities and talent and thus is influenced by the work environment. A work environment that fosters creativity and innovation is usually characterized by support from superiors, opportunities to learn and develop, and an incentive system that encourages creativity. Therefore, to encourage innovative work behaviour, government agencies need to create a work environment conducive to innovation.

The government has initiated several digitization schemes in Indonesia to improve e-government and online one-stop services. In doing this, the innovative work behaviour of freshly graduated employees plays a critical role in deciding the success of digitalization. Thinking creatively, embracing new technology, and seeking novel solutions to old challenges are often regarded as indicators of innovative work activity. Innovative employees can adapt to technological developments and use them to boost productivity and service quality (Kraus *et al.*, 2023; Lukaszewski & Eubanks, 2019; Moon, 2002). Considering all these, this study aims to analyze the effect of service digitalization and innovative work behaviour on the performance of fresh graduate employees in Indonesia, using a quantitative approach to test the hypothesis that digitalization services and innovative work behaviour significantly affect the performance of fresh graduate employees in Indonesia.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Digitalization of Teaching Method

Digitalization of teaching method refers to transforming services provided by the government from traditional systems to digital technology-based. This concept includes using information and communication technology to provide more efficient, faster, and transparent services to the public. According to OECD (2016), digitization of teaching method aims to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve the quality of teaching method. Janssen and Estevez (2013) reveal that digitalization can increase government transparency and accountability and improve interactions between government and citizens. E-government implementation is positively related to efficiency and transparency in the fresh graduate, digitalization supports innovation in administrative processes and teaching methods, and the application of digital technology improves employee productivity. Digitalization enhances the accessibility and effectiveness of teaching method. Digital tools accelerate the innovation process in government organizations, and employee performance improves by adopting better technology and integrated information systems (Fichman et al., 2014). In Indonesia, the government has launched various digitalization initiatives, such as e-government, e-procurement, and online-based one-stop services, aiming to facilitate public access to education and reduce bureaucratic red tape (Kominfo, 2020). These initiatives align with the global trend towards digitalization of government services, as demonstrated by the OECD's insights. By embracing digital teaching methods, the Indonesian government can streamline processes, improve citizen engagement, and enhance the overall quality of education. Furthermore, the integration of digital technology in administrative processes has the potential to spark innovation and increase efficiency, further benefiting education and public services.

2.2. Innovative Work Behavior

Innovative work behaviour refers to the actions and initiatives of individuals in seeking new and creative solutions to problems in the work environment. West and Farr (1989) define innovative work behaviour as introducing and applying new ideas to improve individual, group, or organizational task performance. Employees with innovative work behaviour tend to be more adaptive to change, able to adopt new technologies, and more proactive in finding new ways to improve productivity. Digitalization supports operational efficiency and quality of teaching methods; the use of digital technology is directly related to an increase in employee innovative behaviour, and the performance of fresh graduate employees increases with the support of technology and innovation (Bani-Melhem et al., 2018; Broccardo et al., 2023). Research by De Jong and Den Hartog (2010) shows that innovative work behaviour is influenced by management support, an organizational culture that supports innovation, and opportunities to learn and develop. For fresh graduates, innovative work behaviour is critical given the need to continuously adapt to technological change and society's increasingly complex demands (Pang et al., 2019).

2.3. Fresh Graduate Employee Performance

According to Boyne (2002), fresh graduate performance includes various aspects such as service quality, speed in responding to community needs, and community satisfaction with the services provided. Research by Brewer and Selden (2000) shows that the performance of fresh graduate employees is influenced by motivation, competence, and organizational support. In the research, the findings are that digital transformation in the fresh graduate

increases operational effectiveness, digitalization encourages employees to engage in innovative behaviour and improved employee performance is related to increased use of technology and innovation support (Gressgård et al., 2014; Huu, 2023; Osman et al, 2016).

2.4. The Relationship Between Service Digitalization, Innovative Work Behaviour, and Employee Performance

Digitalization of teaching method can potentially improve the performance of fresh graduate employees through various mechanisms. First, digitization can improve operational efficiency by reducing the time and cost required to complete administrative tasks. A study by Mergel et al. (2019) shows that digital technology can speed up work processes and improve data accuracy. Secondly, digitalization can increase transparency and accountability, increasing public trust in government and employee motivation to perform better (Bertot et al., 2010). digital transformation provides significant support for increased innovation in the fresh graduate, employees who have access to advanced technology show higher innovative behaviour (Rahmat et al., 2022). Employee performance also increases with digital facilities and support for innovation.

Innovative work behaviour also plays an essential role in improving the performance of fresh graduate employees. Innovative employees tend to adapt more quickly to new technologies and look for creative ways to utilize them. Research by Scott and Bruce (1994) shows that innovative work behaviour positively affects individual and organizational performance. In digitization, innovative employees can identify opportunities to improve work processes and performance and provide better services to the community. The implementation of digital technology improves organizational performance, digital technology serves as a critical driver for innovation in the fresh graduate and employee performance is improved by influential and innovative digital strategies (Khin & Ho, 2020; Martínez-Caro et al., 2020). Digital innovations improve operational efficiency in the fresh graduate; employees are more creative and innovative with the support of digital technology and employee efficiency and performance improve with digitalization and innovation (Gajdzik & Wolniak., 2022).

Several studies have examined the relationship between service digitalization, innovative work behaviour, and fresh graduate employee performance. For example, a study by Moon (2002) found that implementing e-government in South Korea has improved administrative efficiency and employee performance. A study by Damanpour and Schneider (2006) showed that organizations supporting innovation tend to perform better. In Indonesia, recent research revealed that service digitalization and innovative work behaviour positively impact employee performance in several local government agencies (Pribadi et al., 2022; Suwanto et al., 2022).

3. Method

2.1. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative research design with a quantitative cross-sectional survey approach. This approach was chosen because it allows data collection from a broad sample at a single point in time to describe the relationship between the variables studied comprehensively and provide a snapshot of a population's current behaviours, attitudes, and beliefs (Cohen et al., 2007; Gay et al., 2009).

2.2. Participants

A total number of 300 fresh graduate employees working in various government agencies in Indonesia voluntarily participated in the study. While selecting sampling, the stratified sampling random sampling method was used, in which the sample was taken randomly from predetermined strata based on criteria such as type of agency, region, and position level (Cohen et al., 2007; Gay et al., 2009). Accordingly, the participants are between 30 and 50 years old. Of 300 participants, 55% are male employees, and 45% are females. In terms of their educational background, 60% of respondents have a bachelor's degree, 30% have a master's degree, and 10% have education at the doctoral level. Moreover, work Experience: Most respondents have work experience between 5 and 15 years.

2.3. Data Collection, Procedure and Analysis

The data were collected using a questionnaire designed to measure the studied variables. This questionnaire consists of several parts, beginning with the demographic section and collecting information about the characteristics of respondents, such as age, gender, education level, and work experience. Additionally, data was collected by three 5-point Likert-type scales (1=Strongly Disagree, 5=Strongly Agree). First, service digitalization is measured, covering aspects such as information technology, process automation, and accessibility of digital services. Then, innovative work behaviour is measured, including the ability to adopt new technologies, work creativity, and proactively seek new solutions. Lastly, employee performance is measured using various performance indicators such as work efficiency, service quality, and community satisfaction.

To ensure the research instrument's validity and reliability, a pilot test is followed to assess the clarity and appropriateness of the instrument, allowing for any necessary revisions. Data are collected through multiple channels, including email, online surveys, and direct distribution, to ensure a diverse and representative sample. Once the data has been collected, it will be processed by entering it into statistical software such as SPSS and AMOS. The next stage involves conducting rigorous statistical analyses to test the formulated research hypotheses and interpret the results within the study context.

The collected data were subjected to various statistical techniques to ensure robust analysis and accurate interpretation. Descriptive statistics were employed to provide an overview of the sample characteristics and the distribution of each variable. Before conducting regression analysis, a series of classical assumption tests were performed, including normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests. These tests were essential to confirm that the data met the necessary assumptions for valid regression analysis. To test the research hypothesis, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted, examining the influence of service digitalization and innovative work behaviour on the performance of fresh graduate employees. This approach enabled the identification of the specific effects of these independent variables on employee performance, thereby offering valuable insights into the factors driving workplace outcomes among recent graduates.

2.4. Ethical Issues

This study addressed the ethical aspects of research by ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of respondents. Respondents were given complete information regarding the purpose of the research and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without

consequences. Informed consent was also obtained from each respondent before data collection.

3. Findings and Discussion

The findings of the CFA confirm the measurement instrument’s validity, as all items in the questionnaire exhibit factor loadings exceeding 0.5. This indicates that the items are strongly correlated with the underlying constructs they are intended to measure, supporting the instrument’s validity for assessing the relevant constructs. Additionally, the reliability of the scales was established through Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients, with values of 0.88 for Service Digitalization, 0.85 for Innovative Work Behaviour, and 0.87 for Employee Performance. These values surpass the commonly accepted threshold of 0.7, demonstrating that the instruments used in this study are reliable and consistently measure the respective constructs. Together, these findings underscore the robustness of the instrument in capturing the dimensions of service digitalization, innovative work behaviour, and employee performance.

The study findings indicate that fresh graduate employees perceive the digitization of services in their workplace positively, with an average score of 4.2 on a scale of 1 to 5, suggesting that service digitalization is satisfactory. Additionally, employees exhibit a high level of innovative work behaviour, with an average score of 4.0, reflecting their ability to contribute novel ideas and solutions within the organization. Employee performance is also rated favourably, with an average score of 4.1, indicating that fresh graduates generally perform well in their roles. The classical assumption tests conducted further validate the robustness of the analysis. The normality test confirms that the data is normally distributed, as skewness and kurtosis values fall within the acceptable range of -2 to +2 (Hair et al., 2014; George & Mallery, 2010). The multicollinearity test reveals no multicollinearity issues, with all independent variables having a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value of less than 5. Additionally, the Glejser test results show no heteroscedasticity, fulfilling the assumption of homoscedasticity. These statistical results reinforce the reliability and validity of the data for further analysis.

The multiple linear regression analysis results to test the effect of service digitalization and innovative work behaviour on fresh graduate employee performance are as follows. The regression model’s R-squared value is 0.65, which means that service digitalization and innovative work behaviour can explain 65% of the variation in fresh graduate employee performance.

Table 1.
R square results

Variables	Regression Coefficient	t- value	p-value
Service Digitalization → Innovative Work Behavior	0.35	5.67	.000
Innovative Work Behavior → Employee Performance	0.35	5.67	.000
Service Digitalization → Employee Performance	0.45	7.89	.000

These results show that service digitalization significantly impacts innovative work behaviour (coefficient = 0.35, $p < .001$). This means that improvements in service digitalization in the work environment encourage employees to be more creative in carrying out their tasks. This finding aligns with the theory proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2016), which states that information technology improves operational efficiency and effectiveness, encouraging innovative behaviour. Innovative Work Behaviour and Employee

Performance and Innovative work behaviour were also found to significantly impact employee performance (coefficient = 0.45, $p < .001$). Employees who exhibit innovative behaviours tend to have better performance. This supports the findings of De Jong and Den Hartog (2010), who stated that innovation in work improves productivity and quality of work outcomes.

Service digitalization also significantly impacts fresh graduate employee performance (coefficient = 0.35, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that implementing digital technology in teaching improves efficiency and employee performance. This finding is consistent with previous research by Moon (2002), who found that e-government improves administrative performance in South Korea. This study found that service digitalization and innovative work behaviour significantly positively impact fresh graduate employee performance. Service digitalization encourages innovative work behaviour, which in turn improves employee performance. These findings provide empirical evidence supporting the importance of digital technology implementation and innovation in efforts to enhance fresh graduate performance in Indonesia. Government agencies are advised to continue adopting digital technology and creating a work environment that supports innovation to achieve better performance.

4. Conclusion

The results showed that service digitalization significantly positively impacts employees' innovative work behaviour. In addition, innovative work behaviour was also shown to contribute considerably to improving employee performance. These findings indicate that integrating technology into daily work can encourage innovation and productivity in fresh graduates. Based on these findings, this study offers three practical implications for government agencies, as given below. First, government agencies must continue investing in digital technology to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching methods. Second, to encourage a culture of innovation, organizations need to create a culture that supports innovation by providing management support and opportunities for training and development. Third, government agencies must focus on developing employee competencies through relevant training programmes to improve performance.

In-service training should move beyond traditional models, and continuous learning paths should be disseminated to allow employees to improve their abilities, keep up with technological changes, and foster new thinking. In addition, given the importance of establishing competencies in performance improvement, in-service training should be targeted to the unique skills and abilities necessary for each worker's function. Providing employees with digital learning platforms, online courses, or blended learning opportunities should be implemented in in-service training programs to improve work performance and innovation. Lastly, in-service training programs should enable employees to cooperate, exchange expertise, and learn from one another's experiences.

Despite the valuable insights this research offers, it is not free from limitations. The first limitation is the generalizability of the findings, which is constrained by the sample size and composition and may not accurately represent the broader population of fresh graduate employees in Indonesia. Second, the reliance on self-reported data introduces the potential for respondent bias, as participants' subjective perceptions may have influenced their responses. Additionally, using a cross-sectional research design limits the study's ability to establish causality, as it captures the relationships between variables at a single point in time, precluding any conclusions about longitudinal cause-and-effect dynamics. These limitations

should be considered when interpreting the results and applying the findings to broader contexts.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need approval from the ethics committee according to the research integrity rules in their country. Informed consent was also obtained from each respondent before data collection to ensure respondents' confidentiality and anonymity. Respondents were given complete information regarding the purpose of the research and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without consequences. (Date of Confirmation: 14/06/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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